

IMPROVING STUDENTS' WRITING SKILLS BY USING SOCIAL MEDIA

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Anotatsiya

Ushbu maqola bakalavr talabalarining yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanish istiqbollarini ochib berishga qaratilgan. Ushbu muammoni aniqlash uchun turli usullar, so'rov, guruh testi, talabalar bilan bahs-munozaralar o'tkazildi. Ma'lumotlar yig'ilgandan so'ng, tadqiqotchi talabalarning yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishni tahlil qilindi. So'rovnoma universitet talabalari o'rtasida ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, xususan Telegram, Facebookdan foydalanish tendensiyalarini o'rganishga yordam berdi. Guruh muhokamasida talabalar yozish ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanish uchun o'z fikrlari va munosabati haqida yetarli ma'lumot to'plashga yordam berishdi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, ESL o'quvchilari, Facebook, Telegram, muhokama guruhi*

Аннотация

Использование социальных сетей влияет на жизнь каждого студента. Эта статья направлена на раскрытие перспективы использования социальных сетей для развития навыков письма студентов бакалавриата. Для выявления данной проблемы экспериментируются различные методы, опрос, групповое тестирование, диспуты со студентами. После сбора данных исследователь проанализировал использование социальных сетей для развития навыков письма учащихся. Опрос помог изучить тенденции использования социальных сетей, в частности Telegram, Facebook среди студентов вузов. В групповом обсуждении студенты помогли собрать достаточно

информации об их мнении и отношении к использованию социальных сетей для улучшения навыков письма.

Ключевые слова: *социальные сети, учащиеся ESL, Facebook, Telegram, дискуссионная группа.*

Annotation

The use of social media has impact on every student's life. This article aims to reveal the prospect of using social media to evolve undergraduate student's writing skills. To identify this issue, a variety of methods, a survey, group test, debates with students are experimented. After collecting the data, researcher analyzed the use of social media to develop writing skills of students. A survey helped to examine the trends of employing social media particularly Telegram, Facebook among university students. In group discussion, students helped to collect enough information about their opinion and attitude to use social media for improving writing skills.

Keywords: *Social medias, ESL learners, Facebook, Telegram, discussion group*

Introduction

Writing is a core skill in academic field, in particular in a higher education while technology has affected all students' life, as well as, in education. In today, using social media is growing up day by day, which is also being used for educational purposes. The use of social media for educational purposes is little explored in our country. Although the popularity of social media as a tool for language teaching inside and outside class, the role of social media concentrated on investigating the trends of its use among students.

Literature Review and Methodology

Developing the Internet illustrates to increase the use of social media throughout the globe. Safco states social media as “user-generated content; blogs, audio, video, music, news, photos, tweets—working together with digital technology in [an] environment [where] everything is accessible from everywhere and everything is connected”. Grahl divided social media into six distinct groups including social news, social networks,

bookmarking sites, blogging, micro blogging and media sharing. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Telegram are some of the Social Networking Sites resulting from social media technology. Technology helped instruction is more productive than traditional teaching methods to assist students in language acquisition. Using social media like Facebook and Twitter assisted students to develop their writing skills and vocabulary. (Li, 2010; Yunus et al. 2012). On the other hand, Schmidt and Brown mentioned that the use of social media ought to taken as combination of online and traditional classroom teaching. Warschauer used the laptops to improve writing skills. His findings revealed that there existed an important development in students' writing as use of laptops assisted them to easily access the information to plan their writing, in drafting the papers and publishing their works after having immediate feedback and frequent revision.

Most of students have easy access to social media through their mobile phones, laptops and language teachers used some social media to improve writing skills. The result of study shows that active participation of students is in Telegram and Facebook helps them improve writing skills. During group discussion students conveyed their point of view that easy access to Telegram and Facebook made it convenient for them to use Telegram and Facebook for language practice than the limited time available in classroom. They could visit the writing group discussion chat groups on Telegram and Facebook. For the reason that Omar, Amin Embi, and Yunus are point of view that "Facebook has become a significant part of students' lives, utilizing the tool in a pedagogically sound approach could benefit ESL learners in practicing the language outside their classrooms". Facebook and Telegram provide a group for extending the traditional class by using technology in language acquisition according to students' interest and participation in this digital age. Students shared their experience and enjoyment and expressed their opinion and ideas about a sort of topics on Telegram chat and Facebook rather than traditional classroom environment.

Telegram group enables students to communicate with other groupmates and talk with another friend without time control. Students emphasized they can read their groupmates' post on the Telegram discussion group, and they were also encouraged to share their

personal opinions given the topics. Besides, they can ask several questions and take their replies from others. That group helped them read and comment on other student's questions. One student said that he read and reread her message from sending to the group which assisted her to self-correct her mistakes. As well as, when students write their comment on others post, they repeat this situation on Facebook. Majority of students shared their experience that when they read their friends' posts written in English, they became more conscious of their own writing. When they have some misunderstandings to the words, they consulted the dictionary to search the meanings or definitions of any new words employed by their groupmates on the discussion group. Students take this from motivation and they want to continue this activity to learn through interaction with groupmates and teacher. To sum up, using Facebook or Telegram as an innovative tool for language teaching helps to evolve amazing attitudes and relationships, attract students' attention, motivate them to participate, encourages a collaborative environment.

Most students are active on social media and there exist several ways of improving writing skills:

1. Engaging with the language
2. Expressing yourself succinctly
3. Developing a writing style
4. Learning from the experts
5. Building confidence
6. Being conscious of your grammar

Social media has a positive effect on students' writing skills as given ways. On social media, students are able to use creativity with the language. In other words, they have better understanding of how it works.

Conclusion

From point of view that our classes are needed to upgrade to incorporate social media in order to engage students in the digital period. The study displays that students' easy access to Telegram and Facebook makes it a potential tool to be employed in language teaching to facilitate language learning. The students could improve their writing skills since they were

encouraged to write in an organized way in a stress-free environment supplied by Telegram and Facebook. The use of them rose the student teacher interaction and cooperated the students to learn from their teachers and groupmates through collaborative learning experience. On the other hand, social media ought not to be seen as a replacement of traditional classroom learning but as a tool to help the language teaching in class.

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